

Exploring the Impact of Age and Gender on Perceived Talent Management...

Exploring the Impact of Age and Gender on Perceived Talent Management in the Banking Industry: A Cross-Sectional Survey (Age and Gender's Impact on Talent Management in Banking)

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Abstract

This study investigated the perceived impact of talent management on banking industry employees, focusing on age and gender. A total of 822 participants, including 276 managers and 522 high-potential employees, were surveyed from 276 banks in Karachi and interior Sindh. The study identified several variables related to talent management, including talent management strategy, talent attraction and retention, staffing practices, talent development, and employees' concerns and rewards. The results suggest that a well-defined talent management strategy, attractive compensation packages, a diverse and qualified workforce, ongoing talent development, and effective communication and recognition of employee contributions are critical factors in attracting and retaining talent in the banking industry. The study found no significant association between age or gender and perceived talent management in the banking industry. However, self-reported data and industry focus limit the study's generalizability.

Keywords: Talent Management, Banking Industry, Age, Gender, Employee Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary world, "talent" has become a highly sought-after quality in individuals working for an organization (Jooss, McDonnell & Burbach, 2021). It refers to an individual's natural abilities or skills that allow them to perform a specific task with exceptional proficiency (Gallardo-Gallardo, Dries & González-Cruz, 2013). Possessing talent in a

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particular area can lead to enhanced performance and increased chances of success (Jooss, McDonnell & Burbach, 2021, Gallardo-Gallardo, Dries & González-Cruz, 2013). The talent possessed by employees can be a crucial factor in determining the success of an organization (Jooss, McDonnell & Burbach, 2021, Gallardo-Gallardo, Dries & González-Cruz, 2013). The distinct approaches employees bring to their work, based on their unique talents, can help the organization achieve a competitive advantage (Guzmán, V. E., Muschard, B., Gerolamo, M., Kohl, H., & Rozenfeld, H. (Guzmán et al., 2020). Talent management is a crucial part of retaining talented employees in an organization, and it is the responsibility of human resource management to implement effective talent management strategies. These strategies focus on identifying and developing employees' potential in the long term, ensuring that they are appropriately utilized and motivated to perform at their best (King & Vaiman, 2019). By investing in talent management, organizations can create a work environment that fosters growth and development, leading to achieving their goals. (Hongal, & Kinange, 2020).

Technological advancements and industry have created a need for specialized talent, especially in banks. The recent financial crisis has highlighted the importance of identifying and addressing unpleasant practices in the financial sector. This concern has led to industries adopting more complex operational principles, which require skilled professionals in areas such as the Internet of Things, robotics, artificial intelligence, and big data (Theodorsson, Gudlaugsson & Gudmundsdottir, 2022). As a result, there is now a growing demand for specialists like data scientists and quantitative analysts (Min, 2018). Hiring new staff is challenging and expensive, especially for banks (Bersin, 2013). Thus, talent management is crucial for businesses. It enables companies to systematically find, develop, and deploy employees with exceptional skills. By doing so, companies can retain essential personnel and maintain high levels of commitment among them (Tej, J., Vagaš, M., Ali Taha, V., Škerháková, V., & Harničárová, M. (Tej et al., 2021). Talent management ensures competent managers are recruited, and essential workers are retained, resulting in more efficient banking operations, the creation of new banking products, and improved customer service (Jelena, Jotic & Maric, 2013).

Talent management is critical to organizational success, but age and gender biases continue to affect it in the workplace (DeNisi & Murphy, 2017). Research has shown that older workers are often seen as less productive and adaptable, while younger workers may be perceived as more innovative but needing more experience (Egdell, et al., 2020). Women also need help with career advancement, including a glass ceiling that limits their access to leadership positions, and often need to be identified as high-potential employees (Schinnenburg & Böhmer, 2021). Despite the importance of gender diversity and inclusivity, there is a lack of understanding of these issues in the Pakistani banking sector (Aziz, Sheikh & Shah, 2022). Future research could identify best practices to promote gender diversity and inclusivity, such as mentoring and sponsorship programs and gender-neutral hiring processes. Banks can retain talented employees and create an inclusive work environment by investing in talent management strategies that foster growth and development (Vokić, Obadić & Ćorić, 2019). Addressing age and gender biases in talent management practices is crucial to organizational success, as highlighted in this research on the impact of age and gender on perceived talent management in the banking industry of Pakistan.

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MATERIALS & METHODS

Study Design and Participants

This research involved a cross-sectional survey conducted over one year, from 2019 to 2020. The study participants were high-potential employees and managers from various private and public sector banks in Sindh, Pakistan. The banking industry in Sindh is diverse, including Islamic, microfinance, and international scheduled banks, all of which were included in the study to provide a comprehensive understanding of talent management practices in the region.

Sample Selection and Recruitment

This study utilized a cluster sampling method to select participants from scheduled banks in Sindh province, divided into six divisions: Hyderabad, Karachi, Mirpurkhas, Sukkur, Larkana, and Nawab Shah. The total population of employees in each division was found to be 851. The sample consisted of 276 managers and 552 high-potential employees recruited through a random sampling technique. To obtain managers' perceptions regarding the bank's approach to talent management, branch/operational managers were contacted. Meanwhile, two high-potential employees from grades 1 or 2 were randomly selected from the sampling frame provided by the manager, with the prior consent of the manager. In addition, employees on leave or who had been employed for less than six months were excluded from the sampling frame for high-potential employees.

Sample Size

The study combined the population of all six districts and divided the total by 6 to get the population of each bank in Karachi. The study multiplied the results by 2 to reflect one-third of the population for the computation of the representative sample because Karachi is an important financial centre with a sizable population. The study gathered 32.2% of the overall population from the population of all divisions for the chosen divisions to achieve the necessary determined sample size.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cochran's formula} &= \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \\ &= \frac{8511}{1+851(0.05)^2} \\ &= \frac{8511}{1+851(0.0025)} \\ &= 274 \text{ branches} \end{aligned}$$

Survey Questionnaire

This study utilized a survey questionnaire administered to managers and high-potential employees to collect primary data. The questionnaire contained continuous and categorical variables and was translated into Urdu for the convenience of respondents, if necessary. To assess perceived talent management in banks, the researchers adopted the questionnaires

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developed by Dries et al. (2014). The employee-perceived talent management survey consisted of 27 items, divided into nine sections covering talent management strategy, the review process, acquisition and retention, staffing, workforce planning, training and development, performance management, and financial rewards. Each section contained three items. The manager survey questionnaire was divided into two sections: talent management approach and workforce differentiation. All items in both surveys were rated on a Likert scale that ranged from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”.

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection procedure for this study involved obtaining consent from all the selected samples of high-potential employees and managers and ensuring their understanding of the questionnaire to fill in their desired responses and provide their perceptions of perceived talent management. Ethical considerations were taken via verbal and written consent by the participants before starting the data collection, and all information of the participants was kept anonymous under the investigator’s supervision to protect their privacy. The survey questionnaire was distributed via social media platforms such as email and WhatsApp to ensure convenience for the participants. The study was conducted under the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) guidelines (Cuschieri, 2019) to ensure transparency and reproducibility. Using structured questionnaires helped ensure consistency and accuracy in data collection and allowed for easy data comparison and analysis across respondents.

Statistical Analysis

This study used descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze and interpret the data. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used for data entry and analysis. Descriptive statistics, precisely frequencies and percentages, were used to demonstrate the characteristics of the study participants and their responses to the questionnaire. This approach allowed for the identification of patterns and trends in the data. The categorical data were analyzed using the chi-square test for the association to investigate the relationship between perceived talent management and participant characteristics (age and gender). This statistical analysis determined whether there was a statistically significant association ($p < 0.05$) between the two variables. By using this approach, the study gained a deeper understanding of the impact of age and gender on perceived talent management in the banking industry.

RESULTS

This cross-sectional survey aimed to investigate the perceived impact of talent management on employees in the banking industry, with a particular focus on the role of age and gender. A total of 276 banks were selected, with 160 (58%) banks chosen from Karachi and 116 (42%) from interior Sindh, with 87% being private and 13% public randomly selected from both sectors (Figure-1). Most participants in the study were managers and high-potential employees, with 58% of the participants coming from Karachi. On the other hand, only 4.3% of the participants were from Nawab Shah (Shaheed Benazir Abad), the least represented city in the study. A total of 822 participants were surveyed, including 276 (33%) managers and

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522 (67%) high-potential employees. The response rate for managers was 92%, while the employee response rate was 79%. The study collected responses from one manager and two randomly selected high-potential employees from each bank, ensuring equal representation of managers and employees from both sectors.

Figure-1 Proportional distribution of banks from representative Sample

Demographic Details of Participants

The majority of bank managers (92%) in the study were men, and 87% were married. The age range of most managers was between 36 to 45 years (59%). A large proportion of managers held a master's degree (61.6%), and 46% had work experience of 6 to 10 years. As for high-potential employees, 73.4% were male, and 68.5% were married. The majority of these employees were aged between 25 to 35 years (52%). A significant proportion of employees held a master's degree (84%), and 46% had work experience ranging from 6 to 10 years. Only 0.7% of high-potential employees had more than 20 years of work experience. The details of participant characteristics are depicted in Table-1.

Reliability of Data

The study screened data and excluded irrelevant items with a variance below 50% in the matrix. Missing values within 10% were imputed using mean imputation, and the data were checked for extreme outliers and deleted on a case-to-case basis. The reliability of the participants data was checked concerning Cronbach's alpha, and the achieved score was between 0.6 and 0.7, indicating marginal satisfaction. In addition, the reliability of the talent management approach was calculated as 60%, and workforce differentiation was scored as 68%.

Table-1 Demographic characteristics of the participants

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Characteristics	Bank Managers (n=276)	High-potential Employees (n=522)
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	237 (85.9)	405 (73.4)
Female	39 (14.1)	147(26.6)
<i>Marital Status</i>		
Married	240 (87)	378 (68.5)
Unmarried	36 (13)	174 (31.5)
<i>Age Group</i>		
25-35	59 (21.4)	288 (52.2)
36-45	163 (59.1)	238 (43.1)
46-55	48 (17.4)	25 (4.5)
≥55	2 (0.7)	1 (0.2)
<i>Qualification</i>		
Bachelors	12 (4.3)	88 (15.9)
Masters	255 (92.4)	464 (84)
PhD	5 (1.8)	-
<i>Service Duration</i>		
≤5 years	22 (8)	201 (36.4)
6-10 years	127 (46)	280 (50.7)
11-15 years	87 (31.5)	55 (10)
16-20 years	30 (10.9)	12 (2.2)
≥20 years	8 (2.9)	4 (0.7)

*Frequency (%)****Variables of Perceived Talent Management***

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In this survey on perceived talent management in the banking industry, several variables were identified, which can be grouped into categories based on their relevance and connection to each other.

First category: Talent Management Strategy include the organization's provision of good talent management practices (more than 60% agreement), alignment of business strategy with talent management practices (50.7% agreement), and internal development of talent through training, coaching, mentoring, and on-the-job learning opportunities (49.3% agreement). These variables highlight the importance of having a well-defined talent management strategy for attracting and retaining talent.

Second category: Talent Attraction and Retention include the organization's ability to attract top talent through competitive compensation, benefits, or opportunities (47.6% agreement), retention of top talent to enhance employee satisfaction and job performance (44.4% agreement), and tracking turnover across divisions and departments to identify areas of concern (45.3% agreement). These variables emphasize the need to offer attractive compensation packages and create a supportive work environment to retain top talent.

Third category: Staffing Practices comprised of diversity at all levels of the organization (60% agreement), staffing critical jobs with highly qualified and capable individuals (49.1% agreement), and effective workforce planning (22.8% to 40.2% agreement). These variables highlight the importance of having a diverse and qualified workforce and ensuring effective workforce planning.

Fourth category: Talent Development take account of the identification and reward of top performers with career development activities (35.1% agreement), coaching and mentoring as primary methods of developing talent (43.8% agreement), and communication with employees about career growth and development opportunities (33.3% agreement). These variables highlight the need for ongoing talent development to support employee growth and career advancement.

Fifth category: Employees Concerns and Rewards include concerns about the line of sight between employees and the organization's goals (more than 50% agreement), effective non-financial rewards to motivate and engage employees (46.2% agreement), and a competitive pay structure regarding compensation and benefits (more than 20% agreement). These variables highlight the need for effective communication and recognition of employee contributions to enhance job satisfaction and engagement.

Overall, the survey results suggest that a well-defined talent management strategy, attractive compensation packages, a diverse and qualified workforce, ongoing talent development, and effective communication and recognition of employee contributions are critical factors in attracting and retaining talent in the banking industry. Furthermore, the values were not significant ($p \geq 0.05$) for age and gender in all perceived talent management categories. These results indicate no statistically significant association between age or gender and perceived talent management in the banking industry, based on the survey responses of the study

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participants. Therefore, the study suggests that talent management practices in the banking industry may not be affected by age or gender and that other factors may play a more significant role in shaping perceptions of talent management (Table-2).

Table-2 Participants response to perceived talent management questionnaire							
Items/Constructs	Responses on Likert Scale					Pearson Chi-square (p<0.05)	
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Age	Gender
Talent Management Strategy							
<i>Item-1: The organization is very good at implementing talent management practices</i>	24 (4.3)	16 (2.9)	151 (27.4)	196 (35.5)	165 (29.9)	0.937	0.997
<i>Item-2: The organization is effectively aligned with strategic goals of talent management practices</i>	18 (3.3)	18 (3.3)	55 (28.1)	280 (50.7)	81 (14.7)	0.572	0.714
<i>Item-3: The organization's business strategy is aligned with the talent management practices</i>	11 (2)	27 (4.9)	166 (30.1)	228 (41.3)	120 (21.7)	0.626	0.980
Talent Review Process							
<i>Item-1: The organization knows how to attract and retain talented individuals who can contribute to its success.</i>	16 (2.9)	103 (18.7)	95 (17.2)	243 (44)	95 (17.2)	0.636	0.308
<i>Item-2: Rewards and opportunities are provided to employees based on their performance and potentials.</i>	18 (3.3)	103 (18.7)	76 (13.8)	197 (35.7)	158 (28.6)	0.974	0.144
<i>Item-3: The majority of talent is developed internally, through training and development programs, coaching and mentoring and on-the-job learning opportunities.</i>	15 (2.7)	45 (8.2)	154 (27.9)	272 (49.3)	66 (12)	0.910	0.938

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Staffing							
<i>Item-1: The company's workforce is diverse and reflects the broader community to operationalize.</i>	15 (2.7)	27 (4.9)	76 (13.8)	330 (59.8)	104 (18.8)	0.405	0.473
<i>Item-2: Diversity is properly represented at all levels of the organization.</i>	16 (2.9)	89 (16.1)	73 (13.2)	279 (50.5)	95 (17.2)	0.191	0.344
<i>Item-3: The most critical jobs are staffed with highly qualified and capable individuals.</i>	17 (3.1)	35 (6.3)	100 (18.1)	271 (49.1)	129 (23.4)	0.227	0.865
Talent Acquisition							
<i>Item-1: The organization can attract top talent by offering competitive compensation, benefits and opportunities.</i>	12 (2.2)	62 (11.2)	135 (24.5)	263 (47.6)	80 (14.5)	0.238	0.343
<i>Item-2: Newly hired employees are successfully integrated into the organization.</i>	15 (2.7)	40 (7.2)	199 (36.1)	231 (41.8)	67 (12.1)	0.380	0.429
<i>Item-3: The hiring process is efficient and effective, with a focus on identifying and selecting the best candidates for the job.</i>	23 (4.2)	22 (4)	141 (25.5)	227 (41.1)	139 (25.2)	0.607	0.657
Workforce planning							
<i>Item-1: Our organization has the right people in the right roles, with the necessary skills, knowledge, and experience.</i>	16 (2.9)	42 (7.6)	171 (31)	247 (44.7)	76 (13.8)	0.327	0.178
<i>Item-2: Workforce planning in our organization is effective and aligned with business objectives.</i>	11 (2)	83 (15)	110 (19.9)	222 (40.2)	126 (22.8)	0.853	0.510
<i>Item-3: Our organization conducts workforce development activities that support employee growth and development.</i>	16 (2.9)	93 (16.8)	121 (21.9)	258 (46.7)	64 (11.6)	0.581	0.242
Training and development							

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<i>Item-1: In our organization, top performers are identified and rewarded with career advancement opportunities, performance-based incentives, and recognition programs.</i>	16 (2.9)	37 (6.7)	193 (35)	194 (35.1)	112 (20.3)	0.597	0.422
<i>Item-2: Coaching and mentoring are primary methods of developing talent in our organization.</i>	30 (5.4)	42 (7.6)	141 (25.5)	242 (43.8)	97 (17.6)	0.699	0.661
<i>Item-3: Communication to employees about development opportunities and career growth prospects is frequent and transparent.</i>	18 (3.3)	38 (6.9)	160 (29)	184 (33.3)	152 (27.5)	0.353	0.139
Performance Management							
<i>Item-1: There is a "line of sight" between employees and the organization's goals and objectives.</i>	14 (2.5)	92 (16.7)	125 (22.6)	260 (47.1)	61 (11.1)	0.085	0.220
<i>Item-2: Top performers are paid and rewarded appropriately for their contributions to the organization's success.</i>	27 (4.9)	57 (10.3)	198 (35.9)	200 (36.2)	70 (12.7)	0.344	0.089
<i>Item-3: Nonfinancial rewards are effectively used to motivate and engage employees</i>	24 (4.3)	100 (18.1)	128 (23.2)	235 (42.6)	65 (11.8)	0.756	0.144
Financial Rewards							
<i>Item-1: The organization has a competitive pay structure that is aligned with industry standards and benchmarks</i>	21 (3.8)	87 (15.8)	122 (22.1)	242 (43.8)	80 (14.5)	0.116	0.872
<i>Item-2: The organization provides medical aid, insurance, and other benefits that help employees maintain good health and well-being.</i>	37 (6.7)	70 (12.7)	175 (31.7)	187 (33.9)	83 (15)	0.306	0.536
<i>Item-3: The organization provides other types of financial benefits and perks, such as retirement plans, stock options,</i>	18 (3.3)	91 (16.5)	135 (24.5)	233 (42.2)	75 (13.6)	0.542	0.196

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<i>and paid time off.</i>							
Retention of Talent							
<i>Item-1: The organization can retain its top talent for employees satisfaction and job performance</i>	25 (4.5)	43 (7.8)	143 (25.9)	245 (44.4)	96 (17.4)	0.415	0.586
<i>Item-2: Turnover is tracked across divisions and departments to address underlying issues.</i>	33 (6)	36 (6.5)	132 (23.9)	250 (45.3)	101 (18.3)	0.550	0.075
<i>Item-3: Managers hold retention conversations with employees to understand their career goals, motivations, and concerns.</i>	27 (4.9)	20 (5.4)	116 (21)	291 (52.7)	88 (15.9)	0.147	0.700

Frequency (%)

DISCUSSION

This cross-sectional survey investigated the perceived impact of talent management on banking industry employees, focusing on age and gender. A total of 822 participants, including 276 managers and 522 high-potential employees, were surveyed from 276 banks selected randomly from Karachi and interior Sindh. The study identified five categories of perceived talent management: talent management strategy, talent attraction and retention, staffing practices, talent development, and employees’ concerns and rewards. The survey results suggest that a well-defined talent management strategy, attractive compensation packages, a diverse and qualified workforce, ongoing talent development, and effective communication and recognition of employee contributions are critical factors in attracting and retaining talent in the banking industry. No statistically significant association between age or gender and perceived talent management was found, indicating that other factors may play a more significant role in shaping perceptions of talent management.

In comparing the findings of the different studies, it is clear that talent management practices significantly impact job satisfaction and job performance in the banking industry of Pakistan. Awan and Farhan (2016), and Hayat et al. (2018) found that talent management practices positively affect job satisfaction and performance, respectively. At the same time, Ali and Rahman (2006) emphasized the importance of talent management practices in retaining employees. Our study similarly supports the idea that talent management practices are perceived to impact employees in the banking industry positively. However, the studies differ in their findings regarding the role of age and gender in talent management practices. Awan and Farhan (2016) and Hayat et al. (2018) both found that age and gender did not significantly moderate the relationship between talent management practices and job

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satisfaction or job performance, respectively. In contrast, Ali and Rahman²⁰ found that age and gender play a significant role in talent management practices for employee job retention. Older employee's value stability and job security more than younger employees, and female employees face more challenges balancing work and family responsibilities. Jokhio et al. (2019) also highlighted the importance of age and gender in talent management practices, with seniority and experience often prioritized over potential in older employees and gender stereotypes impacting the identification of high-potential employees.

Our study found no statistically significant association between age and gender and perceived talent management practices. However, we did not examine the role of age and gender in detail. Nevertheless, the findings of Ali and Rahman (2006) and Jokhio et al. (2019) suggest that age and gender biases can exist in talent management practices, and organizations in the banking industry should work to develop more inclusive talent strategies that take these factors into account. Gender was not a significant predictor of using digital financial services (DFS) in Zimbabwe. (Chamboko, 2022). In contrast, our study focused on talent management practices in the banking industry and found that age and gender were not significantly associated with perceived talent management practices. While the two studies may seem different, they highlight the importance of considering factors beyond demographics in shaping behavior or perceptions. In the case of DFS usage, factors such as level of education, source of income, locality, and income level were found to affect the use of DFS more than gender or age. Similarly, in the banking industry, other factors such as talent development, compensation, and communication played a more significant role in shaping perceptions of talent management than age or gender. These findings suggest that when designing policies or strategies to promote financial inclusion or talent management, it is essential to consider a broad range of factors beyond demographic characteristics (Galletta et al., 2022, Merhi et al., 2021, Dang et al., 2020). Instead, a more nuanced approach that considers different groups' specific needs and challenges may be more effective. Similarly, talent management strategies may need to consider different groups' unique needs and aspirations to attract and retain talent effectively.

Overall, the studies suggest that talent management practices are essential for enhancing employee job satisfaction, job performance, and retention in the banking industry of Pakistan. While the role of age and gender in talent management practices may differ across studies, it is clear that organizations should strive to develop more inclusive talent strategies that consider the unique needs and perspectives of all employees. Furthermore, these findings demonstrated the importance of a holistic approach to policy and strategy design, considering various factors beyond demographics. By doing so, policymakers and industry leaders can better address different groups' specific needs and challenges, leading to more effective and inclusive outcomes.

The study has several strengths that contribute to its significance and potential impact. Firstly, including a diverse sample of participants enhances the generalizability of the findings to the broader banking industry. Secondly, using a structured questionnaire and statistical analyses increases the study's rigor and reliability by ensuring that the data collected is objective and systematically analyzed. Finally, the study fills a gap in the literature. It is the first to be conducted on bank managers and high-potential employees in Pakistan, providing valuable insights into talent management practices in this region.

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The study also has several limitations that need to be acknowledged. One of the main limitations is that the study relies on self-reported data, which may be subject to response bias. Participants may have provided socially desirable responses or overestimated their organization's talent management practices, leading to inaccurate findings. Moreover, the study is limited to the banking industry in Pakistan, and the findings may need to be more generalizable to other industries or countries. The specific talent management practices employed by organizations in the banking industry should have been explored, limiting the practical implications of the findings. Finally, the study did not investigate the impact of cultural or contextual factors on perceived talent management, which may influence the results. Although the study did not find a significant association between age and gender and perceived talent management practices in the banking industry, it sheds light on the need to consider these factors in future research. Thus, understanding the impact of age and gender on talent management practices could help organizations develop more effective strategies for attracting and retaining talent. Additionally, examining the influence of other demographic variables, such as education and job tenure, could provide further insights into the factors that shape perceptions of talent management. Therefore, the study opens avenues for future research to explore the role of demographic variables in talent management approach.

CONCLUSION

The study highlights the importance of talent management strategies, attractive compensation, a diverse workforce, talent development, and recognition in attracting and retaining talent in banking. Age and gender have minimal impact on talent management. However, self-reported data and industry focus limit the study. Organizations investing in talent management practices can attract and retain high-performing employees, leading to better performance and competitiveness.

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